

ESIP Community Report: 2025 Community Fellows Program

April 28, 2026

Executive Summary

The 2025 ESIP Community Fellows Program evaluation found strong overall satisfaction and clear value for participants, particularly in fostering a welcoming environment, expanding professional networks, and building confidence across key skills. All respondents reported that the Program met their expectations and helped them achieve their personal goals. Fellows demonstrated measurable growth in skills such as facilitating collaboration, networking, and contributing to Earth science initiatives, alongside increased engagement with the ESIP community. A high Net Promoter Score (71.4) indicated strong enthusiasm and likelihood to recommend the program.

At the same time, the evaluation highlights opportunities to strengthen the Program's impact. Fellows reported more limited benefits related to career advancement and community-wide engagement, with relatively few new professional connections and mixed experiences across Collaboration Areas. Key recommendations include establishing a formal program evaluation framework, expanding structured networking and mentorship opportunities, aligning expectations between Fellows and Collaboration Area leaders, and creating more intentional cross-Cluster and professional development activities. Addressing these areas will help ensure more consistent experiences and deepen the program's contributions to participants' career trajectories but also to the broader ESIP community.

Introduction

About ESIP Community Reports

ESIP is a home for Earth science data professionals. As a nonprofit funded by cooperative agreements with NASA, NOAA, and USGS, we bring together interdisciplinary collaborations to share technical knowledge and engage with data users. Community reports are published to respond to community needs, ensure organizational transparency, and to raise awareness on topics relevant to our partners and community members. In some cases, a synthesis report will be published to examine trends in community activities over time. **This report summarizes findings from our 2025 ESIP Community Fellows Program survey (reference Appendix).**

Community Fellows Program Overview

The Community Fellows Program, previously known as the Student Fellows Program, was established as an opportunity within ESIP for early career researchers to work closely with professionals in an interdisciplinary, cross-sector group by working with one of the ESIP Collaboration Areas. In this role, Fellows also offer support running the January and July ESIP Meetings alongside ESIP staff. They receive a \$2,000 stipend, registration for both Meetings, and travel support to attend the in-person Meeting.

The Community Fellows program has been a part of ESIP since 2011. Over the years, the number of Fellows has shifted with there being ten Fellows in the last two years (Table 1). There have been evident positive outcomes from the Program over time, but there has never been a formal evaluation.

Table 1. Number of Fellows participating in the Program since data were recorded.

Year	# of Fellows
2019	9
2020	7
2021	8
2022	9
2023	8
2024	10
2025	10

Findings

There were ten individuals who served as Community Fellows in the 2025 cohort. Of those, seven completed the post program survey giving a 70% response rate.

Fellowship Support

Fellows receive a \$2,000 stipend, registration to attend both the January and July Meetings, and travel support to attend the in-person July Meeting. We wanted to get a sense of how important each of these were to participate in the program. All three types of support ranked as very important, on average (Table 2).

Table 2. The importance of each type of support offered through the Fellowship Program, averaged on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (extremely important).

Type of Support	Average
Paid registration to attend ESIP Meetings	4.3
Paid travel to attend the ESIP Meeting in Seattle	4.4
Receiving a \$2000 stipend	4.7

Related to how much the Program offers in participant support (\$2,000), we wanted to understand how much time is spent on Program activities. Most respondents indicated that they spent 1 to 4 hours/month on average while one indicated spending 5 to 10 hours/month on average.

Participant Experience and Satisfaction

We asked questions to examine Fellows' overall experience and satisfaction with the Program. We found overall satisfaction from respondents, with 100% agreeing that the Program met their expectations, allowed them to meet their personal goals, provided a welcoming environment, and helped them meet new colleagues (Table 3). More respondents were neutral to feeling that their contributions were valued (14%), that the Program had helped them develop new skills (29%), and that it had helped them reach their career goals (43%; Table 3).

Table 3. Percentage of respondents (N=7) agreeing, disagreeing, or neutral to the following statements regarding their Fellowship experience.

Statement	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
The Community Fellows Program met my expectations.	100%	-	-
My personal goals for participating in the Program were met.	100%	-	-
My contributions to ESIP over the past year were valued.	86%	14%	-
ESIP provided a welcoming, positive, and supportive environment.	100%	-	-
My participation in the Fellows program has helped me develop new skills.	71%	29%	-
My participation in the Fellows program has helped me reach my career goals.	57%	43%	-
My participation in the Fellows program has helped me meet new colleagues.	100%	-	-

A few respondents left positive comments regarding their overall experience:

"This fellowship has imparted upon me interpersonal as well as technical knowledge that have shaped existing career goals and created new ones. I am extremely appreciative of ESIP as a space and of this fellowship as a valued component of that space."

"ESIP was incredibly welcoming and valued me as an upcoming scientist and a fellow - much more so than I have experienced before. So thank you, really."

"I found the involvement in the program to be valuable, as it allowed me to work closely with the Cluster in a way that provided insight to topics that were directly relevant to my interests. Additionally, the greater ESIP community and attending the biannual Meetings opened my personal network and allowed me to make more connections, as well as allowed me to make stronger ties to others in the fellowship."

Satisfaction with Program Activities

We also examined satisfaction with activities supported through the Program. Participation in ESIP's July Meeting and monthly cohort meetings received high rates of satisfaction, 100% and 86%, respectively (Table 4). In contrast to the summer Meeting, most were neutral in their satisfaction with participation in ESIP's January Meeting (86%; Table 4). This is likely related to Fellows' short time in the Program prior to the winter meeting. There was some dissatisfaction with engagement with the Collaboration Area (14%) and opportunities to engage with other community members (14%; Table 4). One respondent commented: *"I think the opportunities to engage with other community members were pretty limited."*

Table 4. Percentage of total respondents satisfied, dissatisfied or neutral to the following Fellowship activities.

Activity	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied
Participation in ESIP's January Meeting	14%	86%	-
Participation in ESIP's July Meeting	100%	-	-
Monthly cohort meetings	86%	14%	-
Engagement with your Collaboration Area	72%	14%	14%
Opportunities to engage with other community members	29%	57%	14%

Satisfaction with Community Support

Respondents were also asked to what extent they felt supported through the Program. On average, Fellows felt they received sufficient support from staff, Fellows, and Chairs (Table 5). However, the level of support from the community fell just above neutral when averaged across respondents (3.3; Table 5). This is further evidence that Fellows felt there was a lack of networking opportunities to engage directly with members of the community.

Table 5. The extent to which Fellows felt supported by staff and the community during the Fellowship period, averaged on a scale from 1 (no extent) to 5 (a great extent).

Type of Support	Average
ESIP Community Director	4.7
Other members of the ESIP staff	4.7

Type of Support	Average
Other Fellows in my cohort	4.6
The Chair(s) of the Cluster I support	4.3
Other ESIP community members	3.3

Development of Skills

We wanted to get a general idea of how the Fellowship supported the development of skills throughout participation in the Program. We asked how confident Fellows were with relevant skills before and after their participation. Fellows indicated increased confidence, on average, in all skills listed (Table 6).

Table 6. Confidence in a set of skills before and after participation in the Fellowship Program, averaged on a scale from 1 (not confident) to 4 (very confident).

Skill	Before	After
Communicating my research to interdisciplinary audiences	3.1	3.6 (+.5)
Facilitating collaborative discussions	2.1	3.1 (+1)
Contributing to Earth science initiatives	2.3	3.3 (+1)
Navigating professional networking opportunities	2	3.3 (+1.3)
Serving as a community manager for science professionals	1.6	2.8 (+1.2)

When asked about additional skills gained through the Fellowship, the following were shared:

- *Managing such collaborative yet unstructured work (outside of the structure we provided) in an academic setting was a new experience to navigate, so I feel a bit more equipped to project manage, which seems like an extremely important skill to gain as an early-career scientist.*
- *I gained comfort in facilitating zoom meetings and organizing talks. This isn't something I experienced before ESIP.*

There were a number of opportunities available for Fellows to communicate their research with the ESIP community. However, a small percentage took advantage of presenting at the January Meeting or authoring a blog post (Table 7). A larger percentage posted about Fellowship activities through social media (57%; Table 7). All respondents presented their

work at the July Meeting, but this is a requirement for participation in the Program. Not listed as an option in the survey, Fellows also indicated their participation in FUNding Friday.

Table 7. Percentage of respondents who shared their work in the ways listed below.

Work Shared	Percentage
Presented at January ESIP Meeting	29%
Presented at July ESIP Meeting	100%
Authored a blog post	29%
Posted about Fellowship activities through social media	57%

Engagement and Networking

Providing space for Fellows to network and collaborate with new colleagues is a big aspect of the Fellowship program. Therefore, we asked about engagement with the community and the extent to which they grew their professional networks.

ESIP Engagement: Before and After

Prior to starting the Fellowship, four of the respondents (57%) had never engaged with ESIP. On a scale from 0 (not involved) to 10 (highly involved), the other three respondents selected 3, 5, and 8 (average = 5.3). When asked how involved they plan to be in ESIP following the Fellowship, all indicated plans to continue to engage in some capacity with an average score of 6.

We used the Net Promoter Score (NPS) to examine Fellows' overall support and satisfaction with the Program. When asked how likely it would be for them to recommend it to a friend, on a scale from 0 (not all likely) to 10 (extremely likely), the average response was 9.1 with an NPS of 71.4. An NPS above 50 is generally considered excellent. Only two respondents selected a 7 or 8, classifying them as passives (i.e., satisfied but unenthusiastic). All other respondents fell into the NPS promoter category, which indicates strong support and enthusiasm for the Program.

Growing Professional Networks

When asked how many new professional contacts had been made, 42% selected 0-5 while 29% selected 6-10 or 11-20. When asked how likely they were to stay in touch with others they met during the Fellowship, all responded "very likely" with the exception of one who responded "somewhat likely."

We also wanted to get a general idea of how Fellows felt their networks and collaborations had grown through the Fellowship. We asked how strongly Fellows agreed with relevant statements before and after their participation. On average, Fellows indicated increased agreement for all relevant statements (Table 8). One area that showed little shift was the opportunity for Fellows to present their research publicly. This statement showed strong agreement prior to participation in the Fellowship, so it is likely that many Fellows had existing opportunities through their institution and/or professional society.

Table 8. Agreement with statements before and after participation in the Fellowship Program, averaged on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

Statement	Before	After
I had a strong, supportive professional network.	2.6	3.6 (+1)
I had access to potential collaborators outside of my institution.	2.1	3 (+.9)
My research was visible beyond my institution.	2.4	3.1 (+.7)
I had opportunities to present my work publicly.	3.6	3.7 (+.1)
I felt comfortable reaching out to others in the field.	2.7	3.3 (+.6)
I felt part of a professional Earth science community.	1.9	3.3 (+1.4)
I felt prepared for my career as an Earth data science professional.	2	2.9 (+.9)

Professional Development

Opportunities through Collaboration Areas

A major part of the Fellowship Program is for the Fellow to support a Collaboration Area of the Fellows choosing. When asked if their experience with their Collaboration Area helped them grow professionally, 43% indicated that it helped significantly, 43% indicated somewhat, and 14% indicated that they were unsure. Comments indicated that the experience of Fellows differed depending on the Collaboration Area assigned. Although Fellows indicate Collaboration Areas of interest in their application process, not all Fellows

are assigned to their first choice. In addition, some Collaboration Areas are working on specific products while others are leading a webinar series on topics of interest to the group. Depending on the interests and needs of the Fellow, this resulted in different experiences:

"My Collaboration Area was a little bit disorganized and was a bit harder to network or make impacts since it's mostly bringing people in for talks."

"I felt that working on a collaborative project with the Collaboration Area would be a better use of time."

"I think currently the experience as a community fellow is pretty much dependent on which Cluster you end up working with."

"I became involved with the Cluster last year and the fellowship allowed me to develop a stronger connection with others within the community."

"I met and was inspired by many scientists that I hope will result in major collaborations and contributions in the future."

When asked about other impacts the Program had on individuals' career and professional development, respondents commented:

"Shaping and expanding my research, thanks to the complementary nature of the Collaboration Area broadening my horizons."

"ESIP helped me feel more confident and valued, which is something I have always struggled with."

"Being part of the fellowship gave me confidence that I belong and can learn from different parts of the Earth science community."

Recommendations for Improvement

Respondents provided a number of recommendations for improving the Fellowship in future years. Those recommendations included:

- *I really appreciate how [Community Director] started sharing some useful career-boosting skills with us. Even very small activities, like the quick one we did today where we reflect on the skills we strengthened in this experience, to then apply that to a resume.*

- *I love the monthly calls and having the slack fellows channel. Having the fellows make a whatsapp for the in-person Meeting was huge for us connecting one-on-one.*
- *Maybe facilitate a meeting with the Cluster chairs to introduce the fellow. I had some trouble when I first began contacting them. The previous fellow remained involved, so [they] understood the role of the fellowship and were better at responding to communications and providing expectations.*
- *I'd suggest more interdisciplinary engagement. For managing calls, it would definitely be do-able to have fellows move around Clusters (like Cluster #1 call for January then #2 for February) and meet more people in ESIP (like we did in the January/July Meetings!). This could be a little confusing, however.*
- *I'd suggest more across-Cluster meetings and trying to get people to engage more across disciplines. The Envirosensing Cluster, for instance, focuses a lot on sensors and equipment - which could be helpful for all sorts of other Collaboration Areas.*
- *I think there is a lot of overlap in Cluster subject matter and current efforts, but sometimes it feels very silo'ed, unless you're able to attend every Cluster's meetings. I wonder if there can be larger efforts to conduct something like short term collaborations between Clusters who have similar goals or interests in a moment, or a way to gather and share Cluster updates in a brief but meaningful way (i.e., that people will engage with).*
- *Slack is amazing. Please keep this.*

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings from the survey, we have developed a number of recommendations for improvements to the Community Fellows Program in future years.

Develop a program evaluation plan. The ESIP Fellowship Program has been around, in some form, for 15 years. [An early blog post](#) indicated that the program was originally formed for Fellows to “support ESIP Collaboration Areas that align with their graduate school research interest as one way to gain ‘real-world’ experience.” The ESIP website includes additional language that indicates that the program “provides early career researchers a chance to work closely with Earth science data professionals” with “occasional networking and training events.” A formal program evaluation plan should be developed that clearly articulates program goals, the activities that align with them, and the short and long term impacts the Program hopes to achieve. Such a plan will improve on future iterations of this survey and support further improvements to the Program over time as ESIP evolves as an organization.

Increase opportunities for Fellows to engage with the community. Respondents indicated some dissatisfaction with the number of opportunities available to engage with

other community members through the Program. When asked how many new professional contacts had been made, just under half selected ≤ 5 . Considering Fellows' work with both their Collaboration Area and at ESIP meetings, this number is quite low. Although ESIP has never had a formal mentorship program, these findings indicate that the Fellowship Program could benefit from more opportunities for Fellows to network and connect with mentors. Within the context of the Fellows Program, a Fellow could work on a chapter of their dissertation with the support of an ESIP mentor. Or, mentors might have an idea for a project or publication and could put out a call for interested Fellows to contribute. These types of collaborations require intentional planning to be successful so Fellows are able to offer their unique perspective and are supported in their growth as a member of the Earth science community.

Connect Fellows with additional professional development opportunities. There was little indication that Fellows felt more prepared for their career as an Earth data science professional after leaving the program. Currently there is not a standard professional development training series as part of the Fellowship, but every cohort will come to the Program with different professional development needs. Those should be identified at the very beginning of the Fellowship year in order to determine how to provide those opportunities, whether through monthly cohort meetings, Collaboration Area activities, or training / workshops offered through partner organizations. Outside of the program activities, program leaders should identify ways to share upcoming opportunities of interest to the cohort so they can continue to build relevant skills.

Ensure Chairs and Fellows have shared expectations and enthusiasm for collaboration. Considering the inconsistency in Fellow experiences depending on the Collaboration Area assigned, more needs to be done to ensure Chairs understand the expectations and time commitment for their Cluster to be supported by a Fellow and the co-benefits of effective collaboration. This could be done through the following:

- Prior to the Community Fellows application period opening, staff could host an event for all Cluster Chairs that highlights examples of Community Fellows' work and how they have supported Clusters in collaborative work. This might facilitate the generation of new ideas and opportunities for Clusters interested in collaborating with a Fellow, including across-Cluster activities.
- Chairs could complete an interest form if they would like a Fellow for the upcoming year. The form would ask about interest in mentorship, personal capacity to support a Fellow, and opportunities to engage the Fellow in Cluster activities. This would highlight expectations early on and also make it easier to match Fellows to opportunities of interest.
- Chairs whose Clusters are then assigned a Fellow should attend a brief onboarding to the Fellows program. This could include roles and responsibilities of the Chairs and Fellows, clarify expectations, and also include mentoring best practices. This

would highlight the need for Chairs to support Fellows as collaborators and mentors instead of delegators of specific tasks.

In addition, the survey indicated that many Fellows had never engaged with ESIP prior to the Fellowship. This may make it difficult for them to identify the Collaboration Area that aligns well with their interests. Requiring Fellows to interact with multiple Collaboration Areas during the first few months and then rank preferences based on interest and fit could improve alignment. Fellows could then be matched with Collaboration Areas with clearly defined and shared goals, increasing not only the professional development opportunities for the Fellow but also the opportunities for meaningful and productive collaboration within ESIP. The capacity and willingness of Collaboration Area Chairs to commit to mentorship of Fellows will require further assessment.

To further assess alignment, the Program Director could conduct a first month and mid-year check-in with Chairs and Fellows to help address issues such as lack of engagement or inconsistent expectations (e.g., scope creep). This would allow for mediation or adjustments to placements if necessary.

Identify opportunities for across-Cluster engagement. A couple of Fellows indicated interest in identifying opportunities to connect activities across Clusters where the work was aligned. This could be an opportunity for a Fellow who wishes to return for another year as their familiarity with ESIP grows, allowing them to identify where such intersections might exist as they facilitate meaningful conversations with Collaboration Areas having overlapping interests. It would also allow for a unique experience that further develops skills in project development, project management, community management and collaborative research approaches.

Appendix

ESIP Community Fellows Program Evaluation

Thank you for participating in the ESIP Community Fellows Program. We would like to assess the impact the program has had on you as a participant. Your input will help improve the program for future years.

Please take 10 minutes to complete this anonymous survey about your experience in the Program. Only ESIP staff will have access to the responses. The Community Director will aggregate and summarize the survey results in a report that will be shared with the ESIP community and uploaded to Zenodo. If you have any questions or concerns about the survey, please email alyciacrall@esipfed.org.

*denotes required

*Prior to becoming an ESIP Community Fellow, how involved were you in ESIP? Please select on a scale from 0 (not involved) to 10 (extremely involved).

*Now that your Fellowship has ended, how involved do you plan to be in ESIP moving forward? Please select on a scale from 0 (not involved) to 10 (extremely involved).

*How likely are you to recommend the ESIP Community Fellows Program to a friend or colleague? Please select on a scale from 0 (not at all likely) to 10 (extremely likely).

*How important were each of the following in supporting your participation in the Fellowship Program? Please select on a scale from 1 (not important) to 5 (extremely important).

- Paid registration to attend ESIP Meetings
 - Paid travel to attend the ESIP Meeting in Seattle
 - Receiving a \$2000 stipend
 - Other: (specify)
-

General Experience

*Please select how strongly you agree with the following statements on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

- The Community Fellows Program met my expectations.
- My personal goals for participating in the Program were met.

- My contributions to ESIP over the past year were valued.
- ESIP provided a welcoming, positive, and supportive environment.
- My participation in the Fellows program has helped me develop new skills.
- My participation in the Fellows program has helped me reach my career goals.
- My participation in the Fellows program has helped me meet new colleagues.

Please provide any comments relevant to your above responses.

*Did the experience with your Collaboration Area help you grow professionally?

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, somewhat
- No
- Not sure

Please provide any comments relative to your above response.

[long answer]

What additional impacts, if any, did the Fellows Program have on your career and professional development?

[long answer]

Retrospective Self-Assessment

*Please rate your level of confidence in each of the following skills before participating in the Fellowship and after participating in the Fellowship, using a scale of 1 (not at all confident) to 4 (very confident)?

- Communicating my research to interdisciplinary audiences
- Facilitating collaborative discussions
- Contributing to Earth science initiatives
- Navigating professional networking opportunities
- Serving as a community manager for science professionals

Please provide any comments relative to your above response.

[long answer]

What additional skills, if any, did you gain through participation in the Fellowship?

[long answer]

Networking and Collaboration

*Please rate how strongly you would have agreed with the following statements before participating in the Fellowship and how strongly you agree with these statements after participating in the Fellowship, using a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree)?

- I had a strong, supportive professional network
- I had access to potential collaborators outside of my institution
- My research was visible beyond my institution
- I had opportunities to present my work publicly
- I felt comfortable reaching out to others in the field
- I felt part of a professional Earth science community
- I felt prepared for my career as an Earth data science professional

Please provide any comments relative to your above responses.

*How many new professional contacts did you make through the Fellowship?

- 0–5
- 6–10
- 11–20
- 21+

*How likely are you to stay in touch with others you met during the Fellowship?

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Not likely

*In what ways did you share your work during the Fellowship? Select all that apply.

- Presented at January ESIP Meeting
- Presented at July ESIP Meeting
- Presented at a Collaboration Area meeting
- Authored a blog post
- Posted about Fellowship activities through social media
- Other: [Specify]

Satisfaction with Program

*On average, and excluding ESIP Meetings, how much time did you spend on your Fellowship responsibilities each month?

- Less than 1 hour a month

- 1 to 4 hours a month
- 5 to 10 hours a month
- More than 10 hours a month

*Please select how satisfied you were with each of the following components of the Community Fellows Program. Please select on a scale from 1 (Not at all satisfied) to 5 (Extremely satisfied).

- Participation in ESIP's January Meeting
- Participation in ESIP's July Meeting
- Monthly cohort meetings
- Engagement with your Collaboration Area
- Opportunities to engage with other community members

Please provide any comments relative to your above responses.

*To what extent did you feel supported by each of the following during the program. Please select on a scale from 1 (no extent) to 5 (a great extent)

- ESIP Community Director
- Other members of the ESIP staff
- Other Fellows in my cohort
- The Chair(s) of the Cluster I support
- Other ESIP community members

Please provide any comments relative to your above responses.

Recommendations and Feedback

If you had to give the next cohort of ESIP Community Fellows one piece of advice, what would it be?

What recommendations do you have for improving the Fellowship for future cohorts?

Do you have any advice or feedback specifically for the Community Director who manages the Community Fellows Program?

Please share any additional comments you may have about your overall experience as an ESIP Community Fellow.

Thanks for providing input on your experience as an ESIP Community Fellow and for all you did for ESIP over the past year!